

ECONOMIC EVALUATION OF INVESTMENT PROJECTS

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Abstract: *This article examines the role of investments in the national economy in the economic development of the state, the theoretical basis of their economic efficiency, and the specific features of the methods of assessing the economic efficiency of investment projects.*

Introduction

The presence of a number of problems in the effective organization of the assessment of the financial and economic efficiency of investment projects in our country negatively affects the activation of investment processes, the construction of large objects, the effectiveness of the use of investments. In particular, the lack of thorough preparation of the feasibility study of investment projects, the factual conduct of marketing research on the project, the imperfection of the methodology for determining and calculating risks on the project in advance, etc. Based on the above, the actual tasks of today are to study the assessment of the financial economic efficiency of investment projects and develop scientific proposals and recommendations aimed at finding solutions to existing problems and improving the assessment of the economic efficiency of projects.

In order to create favorable conditions for attracting foreign investment in our national economy, to ensure a state and individual approach to assessing the financial and economic efficiency of investment projects, to strictly limit the facts of bureaucracy, formalism and sansolarity, to increase the responsibility of officials for the results of the examination, the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan has

the, Decisions” on measures to further increase the effectiveness of cooperation with international and foreign financial institutions“,”on measures to increase the efficiency of project work in the base sectors of the economy " were adopted. In addition, the adoption of the decree “on measures to introduce a system of Project Management in the Republic of Uzbekistan”on measures to eliminate a number of shortcomings that prevent the effective implementation of the tasks for complex socio-economic development, timely identification and elimination of factors that are pore to the reforms carried out in our country determines the priority.

Analysis of literature on the topic large-scale work is being carried out in the country in order to carry out large infrastructure projects, to build modern high-tech production facilities, to intensively develop the economy, to actively attract foreign investment. There is no concept of long-term development of sectors and territories of the economy, taking into account the current resources, as well as the Real possibility of attracting investments, first of all, foreign investment. This is due to the fact that there are cases of inefficient expenditure of financial resources, promoting, doing projects that are not economically promising, which ultimately leads to a decrease in the investment attractiveness of the country as a whole." These circumstances require a radical revision of the procedure for the formation of investment programs, mechanisms for its financing, an increase in the transparency and efficiency of the selection of projects proposed for implementation. President Of The Republic Of Uzbekistan Sh.M.While noting the importance of investments in achieving high economic growth and ensuring strong social protection, Mirziyoyev criticized the fact that so far the work on this issue has been carried out by pala-partish, noted the following: "many enterprises have gone bankrupt due to the fact that the projects have not been carefully calculated, investors have not been attracted to their implementation. Commercial banks, which were tasked with making them healthier, were also heavily damaged. Therefore, since this year, the practice of transferring bankrupt enterprises to the balance sheet of banks has been

put an end. As a result of the superficial economic analysis, the projects did not justify themselves even after their admission to use – due to the lack of raw materials, lack of energy and gas supply, inefficiency in economic terms, the production of products remained undeveloped" [1]. D.Gazibekov believes that when describing the essence of investments, it should always be borne in mind that they are associated with various risks and expected income. The ability of money to generate income depends on the resources from which the money comes and what it is spent on, that is, where the money comes from and what it is invested in. Also, an inextricable link is observed between the reliability of capital resources and the correctness of the investment of funds. Investment differs from other funds by these signs[2].

Investments in the financial and economic justification of real assets can be carried out by carrying out activities related to financing and financing. Financial analysis shows that keladigan samarcanding every participant involved in labor protection has the necessary opportunities for the development of relationships. Economic Analysis esa loihaning National Economist beradigan samarasi point of view analysis. In particular, the World Bank employees (experts) of each Bir loiha within the framework of economic cooperation is certainly crucial to counteract the options that entails Karaganda kölprokktar köllashda kenkazadar[3]. D. Burman, S. Schmidtlar investments and the Bahalarini economy bahalashda kuidagilarga separately karatgan karatgan [4]:

- the impact of the project on the development of the national economy is assessed;
- the resources being entered and the products being received are evaluated in vague assessments that reflect their real value for the national economy;
- the analysis includes directly influencing aspects for the economy (import, export, employment of the population, foreign currency, supply and demand, environmental situation, etc.).k.), as well as indirect effects (effects on other areas, P.k.) is also included;

I.I. Tomb, V.D. Shapiro, N.G. In their works, olderogges described the effectiveness of investment projects as follows: "the effectiveness of investment projects is a category that indicates the conformity of the project with the purpose and interests of its participants"[5]. Accordingly, it is required to evaluate the effectiveness of the project as a whole, as well as to determine the effect of each participant in the project. V. Berents, P.Havaneks believe that in countries with a developed market economy, methods are widely used that are based on an assessment of the effectiveness of investment projects, which can be compared among themselves[6].

Research methodology The main purpose of the research is to develop scientific-practical proposals and recommendations for improving the mechanisms and methods of evaluating the economic efficiency of projects in the financing of investment projects in real sector enterprises in the context of modernization of the economy of our country. Comparison, grouping and economic statistical methods were widely used in the research process. As a result of the research, conclusions were drawn on the evaluation of the economic efficiency of projects in the financing of enterprises of the real sector of the economy, and scientific and practical proposals were developed on the improvement of evaluation methods.

Analysis and results The essence of the problem of increasing the economic efficiency of investments is that it is necessary to achieve an increase in the volume of production, services and profits, as well as the national income, for each cost unit (labor, material, financial). Efficiency is an absolute indicator that shows the economic results of production. In all other convenient description of the project, the project will never be implemented if it does not provide the following: - the income received from the sale of project goods and services will cover the invested funds;

- the profit that ensures the profitability of investments is higher than the level of the firm's desire; - that the payback period of the investment corresponds to the

period suitable for the company. Determining the validity of achieving such results in investment processes is the main task of determining the financial and economic indicators of any project with funds invested in real assets. Carrying out such an assessment is always a somewhat difficult task, as it requires taking into account the influence of a number of important factors: - first, investment costs can be made only once or several times over a long period of time; - secondly, the duration and length of the period of obtaining results from the implementation of the investment project; - thirdly, the implementation of long-term operations can lead to an increase in uncertainty and the emergence of risk in the assessment of all aspects of investments. Table 1 below shows the composition of capital investments by types of capital funds.

Table 1. Composition of investments in the main capital by types of main funds¹

Fixed assets	2019	2020	2021
Total	195927,3	210195,1	239552,6
Residential buildings	20621,9	23200,8	29851,0
Non-residential buildings	33408,1	38172,7	50894,5
Other facilities	23148,7	27039,0	30290,6
Land improvements	127,3	285,9	277,1
Machinery and equipment, total	107305,8	110493,8	113863,9
Transport equipment	16588,2	12415,2	14574,5
Information, computer and telecommunication (ICT) equipment	3194,8	7347,0	5325,6
Other machinery and equipment	87522,7	90731,6	93963,8
Resources of animals bringing products on a regular basis	2418,9	2843,0	3656,8
Resources of trees, crops and plantings that produce products on a regular basis	372,0	880,7	838,6
Costs associated with the transfer of ownership of non-produced assets	198,1	225,0	138,2
Computer software and databases	28,7	25,2	98,6
Originals of entertainment, literary and artistic works	3,7	1,6	0,8
Research and development	5,9	86,5	30,8
Exploration and evaluation of mineral reserves	763,7	26,7	96,4

The main criterion for the selection of investment projects at the World Bank is the discounted modern value of benefits after excluding costs. Both revenues and costs will increase during the implementation of the project. In order for the project to pass the economic competition, it must comply with the following two conditions: - the net modern value of the profit expected from the implementation of the project must not be negative; - the expected net present value of the project should be equal

¹ based on stat.uz data

to or higher than the expected net present value of alternative conflicting projects. Financial evaluation is used in the analysis of liquidity during the implementation of the investment project. In other words, the task of financial assessment is to determine whether the enterprise will have sufficient financial resources to fulfill its total financial obligations in order to implement the project within the specified time. Economic assessment is used to determine the potential ability of an investment project, to maintain the value of the funds invested in this project and to create a sufficient level of their growth rate. Usually, the assessment of economic efficiency of investment projects includes six methods. In turn, they can be divided into two main groups: methods that do not involve the use of the concept of discounting and methods of evaluating cash flows based on discounting. Table 2 below provides information on capital investment per capita by province.

Table 2. Capital investments per capita by region²

Territories	2020-Q1	2020-Q2	2020-Q3	2020-Q4	2021-Q1	2021-Q2	2021-Q3	2021-Q4	2022-Q1	2022-Q2	2022-Q3
Republic of Uzbekistan	1145,0	2588,1	4128,8	6140,3	1213,1	2874,4	4658,7	6861,0	1416,0	3437,2	5345,2
Republic of Karakalpakstan	553,5	1538,3	2649,5	3710,0	609,0	1589,6	2788,4	4189,2	834,1	2135,6	3602,5
Andijan	479,1	1184,6	1988,0	3047,2	630,4	1344,9	2399,9	3470,1	943,5	1961,7	2969,8
Bukhara	830,1	2408,4	5003,6	6295,0	1717,5	4401,8	7277,5	10462,9	3445,1	6138,9	7936,7
Jizzakh	1874,9	4215,9	6573,7	8984,7	1273,4	2857,9	4594,1	6470,7	1246,8	3069,3	5140,0
Kashkadarya	1472,1	3177,0	4485,2	6214,7	774,1	1833,1	3156,3	5148,2	1073,9	2153,7	3397,1
Navoi	3805,8	8387,3	12365,6	15604,2	2942,3	7136,2	10942,6	14672,4	3338,3	8236,9	12480,2
Namangan	923,7	1914,3	2982,0	4229,2	897,4	1922,1	3200,5	4477,8	941,3	2132,8	3473,4
Samarkand	699,6	1594,0	2406,5	3746,0	726,9	1822,7	2955,6	3920,7	895,8	2584,4	3837,5
Surkhandarya	537,4	1241,4	1977,5	3792,2	746,0	1792,5	2846,4	4438,7	888,7	1966,5	3074,8
Syrdarya	1420,5	3070,0	5940,5	8425,4	2026,6	4538,6	6860,7	9257,1	3394,4	5708,6	9618,2
Tashkent	1203,4	2890,4	4504,6	7169,0	1910,8	4060,9	6717,3	9644,5	1700,0	4918,5	7774,1
Fergana	614,9	1302,4	2170,8	2916,0	611,8	1353,5	2274,1	3272,3	704,3	1835,2	2729,9
Khorezm	569,2	1260,8	2036,2	2868,2	592,5	1537,7	2922,6	4344,3	714,2	1767,1	3503,2
Tashkent city	3326,1	7151,3	11386,3	19065,6	3577,3	8943,7	13331,3	20619,8	2972,9	8927,2	14167,6

- When any project is implemented, costs have a primary character in the cash flows related to it. That is, first investments (albeit a certain part) are made, and then cash receipts are realized in return for these investments. Therefore, when calculating the net present value, the value of all cash flows is reduced to the value

² based on stat.uz data

of the initial investment amount. Therefore, when calculating the net present value for a project that requires financing in several stages, the discount rate is not applied to the value at the initial period (initial investment), which is used to bring the values of the cash flows to present value. Because all other values are set to the current value. The present value of the value at that time is necessarily equal to itself.

Conclusions and suggestions

When making investment decisions, it is important to use a scientifically based method of evaluation, analysis, selection and implementation of investment projects. Also, when making decisions about investments, it is necessary to organize the processes of providing them with financial resources in such a way that it is necessary to evaluate the ways of using sources capable of minimizing their cost and increasing the usefulness of the invested capital. Making investment decisions requires the structure of investment capital, its distribution over a certain period of time, and the use of discount coefficients that allow calculating the current value of money; Evaluation of the project's effectiveness is carried out, as well as determining the manifestation of the interests of the participating parties. Although each party carries out its own and different valuation work, the interest in future profits is common to all parties involved. When evaluating the project from the point of view of efficiency, determining the interest and interest of the society, the ecological purity of the product, and how well it corresponds to the development goal of the socio-economic system has a great impact on the financial implementation of the investment project; Economic and financial evaluation is very important when investing in real assets. Any favorable project should not be accepted if it does not meet the following conditions: if the income from the sale of goods does not cover the costs incurred, if the investor who provides the funds for the project does not achieve a return not less than the average profit rate, if the costs are not covered within a period favorable to the investor. Determining whether these conditions are realistic is the key to investing in projects. Evaluating these conditions is a very

difficult process. The main reason for this is the influence of the following factors: attracting investments can be repeated once, all at once, or several times over a long period of time; the period of achieving results can also be very long; as the period of achieving results increases, the level of uncertainty increases, risk increases. The presence of these factors in life requires the creation of investment project evaluation methods. Of course, no one can calculate this quickly and with one hundred percent accuracy in advance. But the proposed evaluation methods help to eliminate the shortcomings (accidents) in the acceptance of investment projects.

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